

INTEGRATION OF LANGUAGES IN EDUCATION

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Annotation: In this article, in the field of education, languages are inextricably linked, one requires the other, and the role of the state program in learning foreign languages is discussed.

Key words: grammar, integration, globalization, foreign languages, program, morphology, syntax construction.

The development of each nation develops with its own traditions, i.e. culture: national holidays, language, religion, faith. Language is not only a means of communication between people, but also an ancient brotherhood for brotherly peoples. 'prigi is also because the similarity of the words to each other, the ease of understanding for us also leads to the strengthening of our mutual relations. Among other things, the Uzbek language is one of the languages with its own position, the reason for its achievement of the status of the state language lies in the great services of the first President of the independent Republic of Uzbekistan, I.A. Karimov. "All good qualities" of that person penetrated the human heart, first of all, with the unique charm of his mother tongue. "Mother language is the soul of the nation" [1] proves the importance of the mother tongue in the society.

Based on linguistic data, we can say that "there are about 20 language families that are known to us, and they are also called "grandfather language". The Uzbek language belongs to the group of "Turkish" languages and has its own place[2].

At the time of globalization, special attention is paid to multilingualism and the promotion of foreign languages in our society. In this regard, many competitive

state programs are conducting their activities. We have to say that for some of our young people, learning foreign languages is a bit difficult, which can be frustrating for them. In this process, first of all, if a language learner knows his own language and its grammar thoroughly before learning a foreign language, he will have the opportunity to learn other languages without difficulty. After all, learning a foreign language without knowing the mother tongue is an irresponsible approach to one's own values. In the educational system, taking into account the similarities in the grammatical structure of languages, school textbooks are created for students, they are taught together with our language, and many measures have been implemented in this regard. In the process of learning foreign languages, we should know that first of all, we should know the written and spoken form of our mother tongue, its construction to a certain extent and be able to freely observe, but then we can learn other languages as well. and understand language integration. If we pay attention to the dictionary meaning of the word "Integration", "Integration" (Latin integration - restore, start again, fill) 1. The state of dependence of individual parts, elements, their a concept that represents integration. 2. The process of rapprochement and interconnection of sciences. 3. Coordinating and unifying the economy of two or more countries." [3]

"Language is the national passport of the people belonging to its own language!" [4] - said our famous writer Chingiz Aitmatov. In fact, the mother tongue is a tool that shows people's nationality and their beliefs. No matter where we go, in the words of the famous artist Anvar Obidjon, we are proud to say that our mother tongue is Uzbek and that we are the descendants of great ancestors like Alisher Navoi, its founder.

In our country, in addition to the mother tongue, special attention is paid to the regular teaching of foreign languages in schools, and state languages such as Russian and English are taught to students. Among them, the "First Step" state program created for elementary school students was developed, which is based on students' mastery of languages. "In this program, it is noted that students studying

foreign languages should learn Uzbek from the first grade, and that students should be taught foreign languages from the 1st grade, but writing from the 2nd grade. "[5] The development of this program also shows how important language learning is in society.

Languages are studied on the basis of rapid integration, as we can see below: for example, in Uzbek, there is a separate section where the concept of sentence fragments and these fragments are studied, this section is syntax, in which the sentence, the parts of the sentence are placed in order, that is, without inversion. For example, Tashkent is a beautiful, great city, and it is customary to use the participle at the end of the first possessive, and second-level parts between them to clarify and expand the meaning. In verse, that is, poetic genres, we can observe cases of inversion, in which the changed order is used to strengthen the meaning. An example of this is:

I know that you are the greatest of all,
I knew that this soil is close to me.

(M. Yusuf, "Uzbekistan")

The order of words in Russian and English follows their own rules. Their connection is that they are similar to each other and grammatically some of them are answers to the same question.

In the Uzbek language, the department that studies word groups is called morphology. "Morphology" is derived from the Greek words *morphe* - "shape", *logos* - "word", "teaching" and means teaching about the forms of words. Word groups are divided into 3 types: 1) independent word groups, 2) auxiliary word groups, 3) separate words." [6] Independent word groups: noun, adjective, number, verb, pronoun, adverb. If we talk about nouns, nouns mean who?, what?, and where? there will be an answer to your questions. For example, an architect (who?), Capricorn (what?), Termiz (where?). The Russian language also has word groups and has its own rules. Below we will observe some similarities and differences: in Russian, the noun group refers to animate and inanimate objects,

who?, what? there will be an answer to your questions. In this, living things: who is a person, an animal? For example, what about Akbar, the planet, a cow, a fly, a mare, and inanimate objects? the question, for example, desk, door, wall, notebook will be the answer. We can observe a lot of relationships in languages. But they differ by some grammatical signs, including other languages. A student who has knowledge of the structure of the Uzbek language will master foreign languages without difficulty. Therefore, first of all, we should know our language and respect our values. Language is the main sign of a nation's existence and its future.

Studying, analyzing and comparing the integration of languages increases a person's mental potential, strengthens his memory, broadens his worldview and expands his thinking. The joint teaching of languages instills in people a feeling of respect and love for this language.

Currently, there is a high interest in language learning in our country, and special attention is paid to this field. Many benefits are created for young people, various certificate scores are taken into account during the admission process to the OTM, and state grants are allocated. Such opportunities encourage everyone to seek and learn more. It is a sacred duty for each of us to be able to properly use such conditions, to organize our time properly, to justify the great trust given to us, and to make an appropriate contribution to the development of our society. Learning world languages and keeping up with our peers, being aware of every area of development, and fulfilling the great and honorable duty of serving our country is the main task of our youth.

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